

ORKG User Experience

This survey is done to obtain feedback from the users of our prototype application ORKG. We will be very thankful if you fill out this survey form and hand it back.

* Required

1. Name

2. Publication at DILS *

3. How intuitive is the user interface navigation? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not intuitive Very intuitive

4. Was the terminology (resources, literals, predicates, statements) well understood? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Hard to understand Easy to understand

New predicate

data format

New: data format

New resource

data format

5. Do you prefer to add predicates yourself or have them predefined? *

Mark only one oval.

- Add myself
- Choose from predefined list
- Other: _____

6. How useful is the autocomplete feature (suggestion) to add a predicate or a resource? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not helpful at all Very helpful

Predicate selection

✔ publish ✕ cancel

New: de

description +add statement

defines

Resource selection

✔ publish ✕ cancel

Mo

Modularity theorem

+add statement

7. How much supervision or guidance did you need to use the application? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not at all All the time

8. How likely is that you will suggest others to try out the application? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Not likely Very likely

UI design

Resources

Add resource

Predicates

Wiles's proof of Fermat's last theorem

[edit](#)

yields	Modularity theorem	edit
+add value		
addresses	Fermat's last theorem (conjecture)	edit
	Taniyama-Shimura-Weil conjecture	edit
+add value		
employs	Mathematical proof	edit
+add value		

[+add statement](#)

9. How much do you like the design of the user interface? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Not at all Very much

10. How can we improve user experience?

11. Any other comments?
